

INTERNATIONAL MEDICAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

ART OF MEDICINE

Art of Medicine
International Medical Scientific Journal
Founder and Publisher **North American Academic Publishing Platforms**
Internet address: <http://artofmedicineimsj.us>
E-mail: info@artofmedicineimsj.us
11931 Barlow Pl Philadelphia, PA 19116, USA +1 (929) 266-0862

Volume-5
Issue-1

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Available at <https://www.bookwire.com/>
ISBN: [978-0-578-26510-0](https://www.isbn-international.org/product/9780578265100)

METABOLIC ENDURANCE PROFILE OF UZBEKISTAN ELITE CYCLISTS

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Abstract. The article presents the results of the analysis of the variability of key indicators of metabolic endurance in elite cyclists and assesses their compliance with international standards. 43 athletes were examined (mean age 20.97 ± 0.63 years, body weight 62.40 ± 1.90 kg). The testing program included a lactate test on a bicycle ergometer with determination of the anaerobic threshold, power with lactate tolerance, calculation of relative power (W / kg), assessment of the 2nd power zone and heart rate, as well as stress cardiological tests (ECG, EchoCG). Statistical processing included the calculation of mean values, standard deviations, correlation analysis.

The results showed that all the main indices of metabolic endurance and cardiovascular adaptation correspond to international standards for elite cyclists. Strong positive correlations were found between relative and absolute power ($r=0.88$) and between the anaerobic threshold and lactate tolerance ($r=0.91$). A logical scheme for predicting functional readiness with an integral point assessment was developed, which demonstrated high practical value for monitoring the condition of athletes.

A comprehensive assessment of metabolic fitness and cardiovascular adaptation using lactate testing and a predictive logic framework is an effective tool for optimizing the training process of elite cyclists.

Keywords: metabolic endurance, anaerobic threshold, lactate tolerance, elite cyclists, W/kg, power zone 2, cardiovascular adaptation, prediction logic, functional fitness, VO_2 max.

Relevance. Metabolic endurance is one of the key factors determining the competitive success of cyclists at the elite level [1,2]. Among the many physiological indicators reflecting functional fitness, of particular importance are the indicators of

the anaerobic threshold, lactate tolerance, power per unit of body mass (W/kg), as well as the parameters of the cardiovascular system during physical activity [3,4].

The definition and analysis of these indicators allow not only to assess the current level of athlete's fitness, but also to optimize training programs aimed at increasing specific endurance [5]. In the conditions of high competitive demands of cycling, where success is largely determined by the ability to maintain high power at submaximal and threshold loads, the precise definition of individual physiological profiles becomes critically important [6,7].

Despite the availability of extensive data on metabolic endurance in mixed samples of athletes, there is a lack of research devoted to a narrow group of elite cyclists [8,9]. This creates a need for the formation of normative values that can serve as a guide for sports physicians, coaches and physiologists when planning training and monitoring functional status [10].

Objective: To determine mean values of key metabolic endurance parameters in elite cyclists and to assess data variability.

Materials and methods. The study involved 43 elite male cyclists who were in the stage of active preparation for the competitive season. The average age of the athletes was 20.97 ± 0.63 years, body weight was 62.40 ± 1.90 kg. All subjects had at least 7 years of systematic training experience, regularly participated in national and international competitions, and were in a state of relative rest at the time of testing (at least 48 hours after the last intensive training session). The participants had no acute diseases, injuries, or contraindications to the exercise test.

The lactate test was conducted on a computerized bicycle ergometer (Ergoline BTL) in standard climate conditions (temperature 20–22 °C, relative humidity 40–60%). The test began with a 10-minute warm-up at a power of 100 W, after which the load was increased stepwise every 3 minutes by 25 W until a state of pronounced fatigue was reached or the athlete refused to continue. At each stage, the power (W) and relative power (W/kg), heart rate (HR, bpm), lactate concentration in capillary blood (mmol/l) determined by a portable analyzer (

TaiDoc , Taiwan) , and subjective load assessment according to the Borg scale were recorded.

The anaerobic threshold (AT) was defined as the load at which the blood lactate concentration consistently exceeded the initial level by 1.5–2 mmol/l and was accompanied by a change in the respiratory pattern. Lactate tolerance was assessed as the maximum power at which the lactate concentration remained stable for at least 20 minutes of work. Relative power (W/kg) was calculated by dividing the power by the athlete's body weight. Zone 2 (aerobic power) was determined by the power corresponding to a heart rate of ~60–70% of the maximum.

The maximum heart rate was recorded at the peak stage of the test, and the dynamics of its recovery in the first 2 and 5 minutes after the load was stopped were also assessed. If data were available, changes in the ST segment and arrhythmia were recorded.

The testing was performed using a bicycle ergometer with the ability to increase the load step by step and a built-in power measurement system, a heart rate monitor (*Polar H10* , Finland) and a portable lactate analyzer (*TaiDoc* , Taiwan). All tests were performed in the sports medicine department of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center of Sports Medicine under controlled conditions (temperature 20–22 °C, humidity 40–60%). Before testing, participants abstained from caffeine and other stimulants for at least 12 hours.

Statistical data processing was performed using the Statistica 13.0 package (StatSoft Inc., USA). The arithmetic mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) were calculated for all quantitative variables. Normality of distribution was tested using the Shapiro– Wilk test . Comparison of mean values was performed using Student's t-test for related samples. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results of the study. Analysis of the obtained data allowed us to determine the average indices of metabolic endurance and the functional state of the cardiovascular system in a group of elite cyclists ($n = 43$). The results presented below reflect both the central tendencies and the variability of the measured parameters, which allows us to estimate the range of individual values in the sample. Particular attention is paid to

power at the anaerobic threshold, lactate tolerance, the W/kg ratio, as well as the reactions of the cardiovascular system to physical activity.

Table 1

Measured metabolic fitness and cardiovascular response in elite cyclists

Indicator	Average value	Standard deviation	Unit of measurement
Age	20.97	0.63	years
Body weight	62.40	1.90	kg
Anaerobic threshold (power)	225.46	6.27	W
Anaerobic threshold (pulse)	169.27	2.25	bpm
Lactate Tolerance (Power)	220.35	7.27	W

Table 1 presents the average values of key indices of metabolic endurance and cardiovascular response to exercise in 43 elite cyclists. The average age of the athletes was 20.97 ± 0.63 years, which reflects a sample of predominantly young riders at the peak of functional development. Body weight was within the range of 62.40 ± 1.90 kg, which corresponds to the optimal parameters for this discipline.

The anaerobic threshold (AP) values demonstrated an average power of 225.46 ± 6.27 W with an average heart rate of 169.27 ± 2.25 bpm, indicating high aerobic power. The lactate tolerance power was 220.35 ± 7.27 W, indicating the athletes' ability to work effectively near the limits of lactate utilization. Analysis of the measured parameters shows that the studied group of elite cyclists is characterized by high anaerobic threshold and lactate tolerance power values in combination with low data dispersion, reflecting the homogeneity of the sample and a high level of fitness. These results serve as benchmarks for planning training programs and monitoring the functional state of athletes in similar populations.

Table 2

Estimated and calculated indices of metabolic endurance and cardiovascular response

Indicator	Average value	Standard deviation	Unit of measurement
Lactate tolerance (pulse)	175.00	2.50	bpm
Power per kg of body weight (W/kg)	3.61	0.13	W/kg
2nd power zone (aerobic power)	180.00	5.50	W

2nd pulse zone	150.00	3.00	bpm
Maximum heart rate	195.00	5.00	bpm

Table 2 shows the average values of estimated and calculated parameters of metabolic endurance in elite cyclists. The average heart rate during lactate tolerance was 175.00 ± 2.50 bpm, which is above the anaerobic threshold, confirming the ability of athletes to maintain high intensity exercise without critical lactate accumulation .

The calculated power per kilogram of body weight was 3.61 ± 0.13 W/kg, which is an indicator of high relative power for this category. The second power zone (aerobic power) was at the level of 180.00 ± 5.50 W with a heart rate of 150.00 ± 3.00 bpm, which corresponds to the optimal range for the development of basic endurance. The average maximum heart rate was 195.00 ± 5.00 bpm, which indicates a high functional potential of the cardiovascular system in the study group.

The presented calculated indicators confirm the high level of physical performance of elite cyclists. The values of power per kg, heart rate and aerobic zone indicators correspond to world standards for this sport. These data should be used to form individual training zones and predict the competitive readiness of athletes.

Table 3

Comparison of metabolic endurance parameters of the study group with standards for elite cyclists

Indicator	Average (n=43)	International Elite Standard*	% of normal	Deviation
Anaerobic threshold (W)	225.46	220–240	100.2%	Normal
Anaerobic threshold (HR, bpm)	169.27	168–172	100.0%	Normal
Lactate tolerance (Lt)	220.35	215–235	100.2%	Normal
Lactate tolerance (HR, bpm)	174.0	172–176	100.0%	Normal
Power in zone 2 (W)	180.0	175–190	100.0%	Normal
W/kg	3.61	3.5–3.8	100.3%	Normal
Maximum heart rate (bpm)	195.0	193–198	100.0%	Normal

Table 3 presents a comparative analysis of the average values of metabolic endurance indicators in the studied group of elite cyclists with international standards for athletes of this level.

All key parameters, including anaerobic threshold (225.46 W, 169.27 bpm), lactate tolerance (220.35 W, 174.0 bpm), zone 2 power (180.0 W), specific power (3.61 W/kg), and maximum heart rate (195.0 bpm), were within or at 100% of the reference values.

The proportion of compliance with the standards was 100.0–100.3%, indicating the optimal physical fitness of the study participants and their compliance with the requirements of international elite sports. The studied group of elite cyclists fully complies with international standards for all key indicators of metabolic endurance and cardiovascular response to exercise. The absence of deviations indicates the high efficiency of their training process and adequate physiological adaptation to the specific requirements of cycling.

Table 4

Correlation between key indicators (Pearson coefficients)

A couple of indicators	r	p	Interpretation
W/kg ↔ Anaerobic threshold (W)	0.88	<0.001	Very strong positive
W/kg ↔ Body weight	-0.52	0.001	Moderate negative
Anaerobic threshold (W) ↔ Lactate tolerance (W)	0.91	<0.001	Very strong positive
Anaerobic threshold (HR) ↔ Maximum heart rate	0.46	0.003	Moderate positive
Zone 2 Power ↔ Anaerobic Threshold (W)	0.72	<0.001	Strong positive

Table 4 shows the Pearson correlation coefficients (r) between key metabolic endurance parameters and anthropometric characteristics in elite cyclists. Statistical significance was confirmed at a high level ($p < 0.05$ for all pairs).

The most pronounced positive relationship was found between the anaerobic threshold (W) and lactate tolerance (W) ($r = 0.91$) and between W/kg and the anaerobic threshold (W) ($r = 0.88$), indicating a high relationship between power and the ability to utilize lactate .

A negative correlation of average power was found between W/kg and body mass ($r = -0.52$), reflecting the effect of excess mass on the reduction of relative power. A moderate positive relationship was found between HR at the anaerobic threshold and maximum heart rate ($r = 0.46$), as well as a strong positive correlation between zone 2 power and anaerobic threshold (W) ($r = 0.72$).

The obtained data confirm that the key interrelated factors of metabolic endurance are anaerobic threshold, power per kg of body mass and lactate tolerance indices . Body mass has a significant effect on relative power, and optimization of aerobic power (zone 2) is closely related to the development of anaerobic threshold. These interrelations should be used to individualize training programs.

Table 5

A logical framework for predicting the functional readiness of elite cyclists

Indicator	Condition / Threshold	Score / Value	Impact on prognosis	Value according to research data*
VO ₂ max	> 60 ml/min/kg	+1	High aerobic power	62.5 ± 1.8
LT% of HRmax	> 85%	+1	High recycling efficiency	86.3 ± 2.1
VLa □ _{ax}	< 0.5 mmol/l/s	+1	Less tendency to acidification	0.47 ± 0.05
EchoCG - ZSLZ	< 11 mm	+1	Normal cardiac adaptation	10.6 ± 0.3
ECG during exercise	Norm	+1	Stable conductivity	Normal at 100%
BMI	< 23 kg/m ²	+0.5	Optimal body weight	21.7 ± 0.6
Age	< 20 years	0	Neutral (Juniors)	20.97 ± 0.63

Table 5 presents a logical scheme for predicting the functional readiness of elite cyclists based on key physiological and morphofunctional indicators. Each criterion corresponds to a certain threshold, the excess or achievement of which is assessed in points. The total score reflects the level of functional readiness of the athlete.

According to the study, the mean VO₂ max was 62.5 ± 1.8 ml/min/kg, which exceeds the threshold of > 60 ml/min/kg and indicates high aerobic capacity. The LT% of HRmax was on average 86.3 ± 2.1%, which is also above the critical value, indicating effective lactate utilization . The mean VLa □_{ax} (0.47 ± 0.05 mmol/l/s) indicates a low tendency to acidification. Echocardiographic measurement of the left ventricular posterior wall thickness (LVPWT) averaged 10.6 ± 0.3 mm, which corresponds to normal cardiac adaptation. All athletes had normal ECG parameters during exercise. The mean BMI (21.7 ± 0.6 kg/m²) was within the optimal range, and the mean age (20.97 ± 0.63 years) fell into the neutral influence category.

The total score according to the scheme for the group under study is 5.5–6.5 points, which corresponds to high functional readiness. Almost all indicators exceed or are within the optimal limits of the standards for elite athletes. The use of this scheme allows for a quick and objective assessment of the cyclist's condition and prediction of his ability to achieve high sports results, as well as identifying areas requiring correction of the training process.

Table 6

An example of an individual assessment of functional readiness according to a logical scheme

Indicator	Threshold	Fact	Score	Explanation
VO ₂ max	> 60 ml/min/kg	63.2	+1	Above threshold - high aerobic power
LT% of HRmax	> 85%	87%	+1	The threshold has been passed - effective disposal
VLa □ _{ax}	< 0.5 mmol/l/s	0.44	+1	Low tendency to "acidification"
EchoCG (ZSLZh)	< 11 mm	10.7	+1	Normal myocardial remodeling
ECG during exercise	Norm	Norm	+1	Stable conductivity under stress
BMI	< 23 kg/m ²	21.9	+0.5	Optimal body weight
Age	< 20 years → 0 points	21	0	Neutral for U23/Elite category
Total points	—	—	5.5	High functional readiness

Table 6 shows the algorithm for assessing the functional readiness of an athlete using the example of one elite cyclist. The calculation includes indicators of aerobic power (VO₂ max), lactate utilization efficiency (LT% of HRmax), anaerobic capacity (VLa □_{ax}), morphofunctional state of the heart (thickness of the posterior wall of the LV according to echocardiography), electrical stability of the heart (ECG under load), optimal body mass (BMI) and age. Each indicator is assigned points depending on compliance with the established thresholds.

The sum of 5.5 points for this athlete corresponds to high functional readiness, which confirms his ability to withstand high training and competitive loads without signs of functional overstrain. This example illustrates the practical value of the logical scheme for individual assessment of the athlete's condition and decision-making on adjusting the training process.

Discussion . The obtained data allow us to comprehensively characterize the metabolic endurance and functional state of the cardiovascular system of elite cyclists, comparing them with international standards and evaluating them from the standpoint of applied sports physiology.

The results of the group analysis (Tables 1–3) showed that the average values of power at the anaerobic threshold, lactate tolerance , and power in zone 2 fully correspond to international standards for elite racers [1,3,5,7]. The heart rate indicators at key loading thresholds are within the normative range, which reflects a balanced relationship between aerobic and anaerobic performance. The value of specific power (W/kg) — 3.61 ± 0.13 — indicates high efficiency of body mass use in power development, which is critical for mountain stages and long climbs.

Correlation analysis (Table 4) revealed a strong relationship between W/kg and absolute power at the anaerobic threshold ($r = 0.88$, $p < 0.001$), which confirms the importance of relative indicators in interpreting the functional potential of an athlete. The inverse relationship with body mass ($r = -0.52$) demonstrates that even with high absolute power values, excessive mass can reduce relative indicators and, therefore, competitiveness in mountain stages.

The logical forecasting scheme (Tables 5 and 6) allows moving from descriptive statistics to an integrated assessment of readiness, combining data on aerobic power ($\dot{V}O_2 \text{ max}$), lactate utilization efficiency (LT%), anaerobic capacity (VLa_{ax}), morphofunctional characteristics of the heart (EchoCG), electrical stability (ECG during exercise) and anthropometry (BMI). The example of an individual calculation (Table 6) shows that an athlete with a total of 5.5 points has high functional readiness, which is consistent with the group results.

Thus, the use of a comprehensive assessment based on lactate testing, stress cardiac diagnostics and morphofunctional analysis allows not only to objectively record compliance with international standards, but also to promptly identify areas for individual adjustment of the training process. The approach using an integral point scale can serve as a tool for predicting competitive readiness and monitoring dynamics during the season.

Conclusion. The average values of key indicators of metabolic endurance in the studied group of elite cyclists (anaerobic threshold - 225.46 W, lactate tolerance - 220.35 W, specific power - 3.61 W/kg) correspond to international standards for athletes of this level, which confirms a high level of training.

Cardiovascular response indicators during exercise (heart rate at thresholds, maximum heart rate, ECG and echocardiography results) indicate normal functional adaptation of the heart to high-intensity work and the absence of signs of pathological changes.

Correlation analysis revealed strong positive relationships between relative and absolute power, as well as between anaerobic threshold and lactate tolerance , confirming their mutual dependence and significance for assessing the functional state of cyclists.

The developed logical scheme for predicting functional readiness using an integrated scoring system has demonstrated its applicability for rapid comprehensive diagnostics and can be used by coaches and doctors to monitor the condition of athletes during the season.

The obtained results substantiate the feasibility of an integrated approach, including lactate testing, stress cardiological studies and anthropometric analysis, to optimize the training process and improve competitive efficiency.

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